

**FINANCIAL HEALTH OF SMALL CAP LISTED PRIVATE BANKS IN INDIA- AN
ASSESSMENT BY CAMEL APPROACH**

Arup Bramha Mohapatra, Lecturer in Commerce, Vikram Deb Autonomous College, Jeypore,
Odisha,India

Manoj Kumar Behera, Assistant Professor in Commerce, Vikram Deb Autonomous College,
Jeypore, Odisha,India

Abstract:

The paper investigates the performance of small cap listed private banks during the period from 2010 to 2020 by using CAMEL approach. Descriptive statistics rank method has been used to rank these banks to find the best among them. The sample of banks for this study has been selected randomly from the list of private bank listed in the Indian stock market. Here the researchers selected 8 banks as the sample size. The financial data/information has been collected from the annual reports of the bank and from the RBI websites. This study concludes with the ranking of banks like the City union bank got rank 1 followed by Karur vysya bank. The worst bank is rank 8 i.e Dhanlaxmi bank followed by south Indian bank.

Key words: CAMEL, Ratio, Small cap private bank, NPA

Introduction:

Bank is a financial institution which accepts money in form of deposits from the public and provides money in terms of loan. In the present economic scenario bank are not only involve in lending activities but also involved in every sphere of economic activities that's why bank is the heart of any developing economy. As banks plays an important function in fiscal stability and the frugality of a country, so supreme authorities always exercise high degree of conservative approach for regulation of banks. Utmost all countries have institutionalized a system known as fractional reserve banking under which banks have to maintain liquid assets only some part of its current liabilities except this banks are bound to maintains sufficient amount of capital adequacy and provisioning against probable default NPA. Because of this, the supervisory authorities had developed a system called CAMEL (Capital adequacy, Asset quality, Management Efficiency, Earnings and Liquidity) for diagnostic bank health.

The CAMEL score determine the overall health of a particular bank. In this approach the best bank have been assigned score 1 and the worst one has been given as high rank depending upon number of banks we consider in our study. In India banks are generally classified in two categories as private and public sector banks. In this paper the researcher had taken sample as eight private sector small cap banks (Market capitalization) for his study. According to SEBI guidelines the small cap companies are those that possess market capitalization of below Rs. 5000 Crores. Small cap companies are always having potential to became mid cap or large cap in long run. So, the investor might be getting bumper return in his invested money in these companies but simultaneously there is huge risk involved in these companies as they do facing a lot of hindrances during difficult period of time. Not only the investor but also the general people who have deposited their life time earning money in these banks have a sense of fear whether their money is in safe hands or not. This is quite clear by watching recent collapse happening in different cooperative banking and national bank like Yes bank. So it is imperative to know that weather the bank is doing right business or not and here CAMEL approach will plays a vital role in this regards.

Review of literature:

Nguyen et.al (2022) has proved that, the impact of CAMEL factors on the fiscal performance of marketable banks in Vietnam. It was found that capital acceptability, asset quality, liquidity and operation effectiveness affect the performance of Vietnamese marketable banks. In the paper (Ray, 2021) the researcher had make an attempt to apply CAMEL rating in 10 small finance bank in India and found that Fin care small finance bank, Surodaya bank was best bank while capital small finance

bank and Jana small finance bank was worst one. In the paper (Gandhi et al., 2020) it was revealed that collectively both public and private sector bank had shown post-merger enhancement in fiscal performance with respect to many parameter of CAMEL model, still there was no statistically significant enhancement in the fiscal performance after the post-merger also there was no significant difference in fiscal performance between private sector and public sector bank after post-merger. The CAMEL analysis paper(Mohammed et al., 2019) was a case study of Bank Dhofar in the Sultanate of Oman and concluded that the bank’s capital acceptability requires some enhancement. The bank must also be increased its input of government security. In the paper(Dr. R. Thamil selvan, 2019) the author was tried to identify the performance evaluation of named Indian corporate banks. The study establishes that HDFC Bank was in First rank, followed by ICICI Bank and AXIS Bank were in Alternate and third positions independently. The intents of (Mishra, 2017)this paper were to assay the soundness and to measure the effectiveness of 12 public and private sector banks grounded on market cap. DEA results displayed that among the public sector banks, the performance of Bank of India, Canara Bank and Punjab National Bank got dampened in the last two times under study whereas among the private sector banks, except Axis Bank which wasn't plant to be satisfactory at each, the remaining private sector banks shows marked thickness at their effectiveness position during the period under study .In the paper (Bansal & Khosla, 2015) it was concluded that the foreign bank and private sector bank out perform in every space with their counterpart. They used multivariate technique to confirm this. (Das & Ghosh, 2006)the researcher investigated the performance of Indian marketable banking sector during the post reform period from 1992 – 2002 and suggested that medium-sized public sector banks performed nicely well and are more likely to operate at advanced situations of specialized effectiveness. From the above discussion none of the researcher focused on financial health of small cap private sector bank which are capable to become large cap in future. This paper is an attempt to check this.

Objective of the study:

- To know which private small cap banking companies is best among the alternatives
- To know which banks have potential to become mid cap or large cap in future and how far depositor money is safe in the hands of these banks.

Research Methodology:

In this study, the researchers used simple random sampling for the selection of sample of banks. The sample banks are like catholic syrian bank(CSB), city union bank(CUB) ,dhanlaksmi bank(DB), jammu kasmir bank(JKB) ,karnataka bank(KB), karur vysya bank(KVB),south indian bank(SIB), developmental credit bank(DCB) and the financial data on the performance of these bank has been collected for a period of 11 years that is from 2010 to 2020 . The data are taken up from annual report of respective banks and analyzed by the help of CAMEL approach.

Data Analysis & interpretations:

Descriptive analysis has done through ranking in each of the parameters of CAMEL rating. Capital adequacy rates ("CAR") are a measure of the quantum of a bank's core capital expressed as a chance of its threat-weighted asset.

Capital adequacy ratio: The capital acceptability rate (Auto) focuses on the capability of a bank to manage with the probable loan defaults and thereby guard the bank against ruin. It's reckoned as the rate of banks capital in relation to its current liabilities and risk weighted means.to calculate the overall capital adequacy ranking of the banks, the researcher used the following ratios like debt equity ratio, government securities to total investment ratio and total advances to total asset ratio. The banks has been ranked on the basis of the result of the above mentioned ratios and shown in the respective tables below.

Table 1 (Capital adequacy ratio (CAR) = $\frac{\text{Tier 1 Captial}+\text{Tier2 Capital}}{\text{Risk weighted Assets}}$)

BAN	20	2017	2018	2019	2020	AVG	RAN						
K	10	11	12	13	14	15	16						K

CSB	1.74	1.1	1.12	2.22	3.85	4.40	5.51	4.46	2.27	1.91	1.17	2.20	3
CUB	0.52	0.44	0.63	1.23	1.33	1.53	1.71	1.7	1.81	2.29	2.97	1.43	7
DB	0.3	0.66	3.36	3.8	3.29	2.78	2.58	3.19	2.41	1.55	4.76	2.59	1
JKB	0.2	0.15	0.14	0.22	2.77	4.31	4.87	4.89	4.89	3.48	2.95	2.19	4
KB	1.62	2.11	1.51	1.91	1.98	2.35	2.64	2.96	2.95	3.08	3.18	2.37	2
KVB	0.07	0.33	0.37	0.41	0.78	0.55	2.53	4.16	4.98	3.92	3.41	2.05	5
SIB	0.29	0.28	0.78	0.78	0.96	2.89	1.45	2.6	3.45	3.34	4.71	1.91	6
DCB	0.97	0.57	0.75	0.91	1.01	0.75	0.79	0.72	0.65	1.16	2.29	1.00	8

Interpretation: In capital adequacy front Dhanalaxmi (rank 1) bank out performs the other bank and Development credit bank, south Indian bank, City union bank needs to be considering for more infusion of capital.

Table:2 (Debt Equity Ratio= $\frac{Debt}{Equity}$)

BANK	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	AVG	RANK
CSB	0.6	1	0.3	0.7	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0	0.4	0.7	0.37	3
CUB	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.1	0	0.1	0.4	0.1	0.4	0.2	0.21	1
DB	0.7	2.4	2.2	1.8	1.3	0.5	0.2	0.5	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.95	7
JKB	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.3	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.4	0.3	0.31	2
KB	0.4	0.4	0.6	0.6	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.6	0.7	0.3	0.42	4
KVB	0.3	0.7	1.3	1	0.7	0.3	0.3	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.4	0.53	5
SIB	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.8	0.6	0.6	0.4	0.8	1	1.3	0.7	0.65	6
DCB	1.5	1.4	1.6	0.8	0.8	0.7	0.7	0.8	0.9	1.1	1.3	1.05	8

Interpretation : Table 2 reveal that city union bank has low debt equity ratio so rank 1 has been given to this bank on the other hand the DCB bank has provided rank 8 as debt portion is quite large as compared to equity which is more risk.

Table 3 (Government securities to total investment ratio= $\frac{Government\ Securities}{Total\ Investment} \times 100$)

BANK	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	AVG	RANK
CSB	78.67	80.81	88.71	89.49	68.69	80.01	81.63	87.75	82.40	78.77	86.66	74.09	7
CUB	80.06	79.76	83.88	86.66	89.32	86.18	93.35	95.14	96.89	96.94	96.78	98.88	1
DB	82.85	90.88	95.49	92.98	84.33	76.03	81.01	74.57	69.60	70.66	66.29	88.86	5
JKB	60.49	52.42	53.41	54.64	57.09	53.55	68.53	76.68	91.09	79.91	89.87	9.82	8
KB	64.06	58.19	63.32	65.99	68.52	71.63	71.14	68.65	84.78	84.31	87.23	88.95	4
KVB	86.07	87.46	88.08	91.27	92.04	90.12	92.00	86.79	88.67	85.15	83.82	93.26	3
SIB	78.6	76.0	87.3	79.7	80.1	73.8	94.6	87.7	87.7	87.8	93.0	94.2	2

	0	9	8	1	6	8	5	2	8	4	1	3	
DCB	77.6 1	76.1 0	80.3 0	72.4 5	77.2 4	77.7 3	91.9 7	82.0 1	78.9 4	76.5 0	79.2 7	80.0 8	6

Interpretation: Under the Basel-III rules, banks have to invest a part of their finances into liquid securities which make up a liquidity content rate (LCR). Under LCR, banks have to invest a part of their deposits and loan exodus within a 30- day period into the so- called HQLA (high quality liquid assets) which could be government securities or treasury bills. here city union bank has been allotted rank 1 followed by south Indian bank rank2 but Jammu Kashmir bank and catholic Syrian bank are two worst performer as their rank is 7and 8.

Table 4 (Total Advances to Total Assets Ratio = $\frac{\text{Total Advances}}{\text{Total Assets}} \times 100$)

BANK	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	AVG	RANK
CSB	58.09	63.28	63.61	64.99	65.39	60.09	50.17	50.05	58.81	62.77	64.89	65.94	3
CUB	59.11	63.43	66.14	53.30	64.40	64.90	68.01	68.36	70.71	73.06	69.52	69.44	1
DB	61.90	63.53	59.67	56.28	54.03	53.44	55.79	52.27	49.73	53.30	52.96	51.83	8
JKB	54.19	51.86	54.89	54.64	59.00	58.60	62.54	60.74	6.35	65.35	59.15	55.57	7
KB	53.42	54.74	57.05	60.70	60.27	61.12	60.00	57.70	67.14	69.36	68.37	60.40	6
KVB	61.30	63.11	63.64	63.08	65.95	67.93	67.78	66.19	66.94	70.06	67.52	67.49	2
SIB	61.97	62.43	67.58	63.89	65.89	63.25	65.03	62.43	65.99	67.94	66.41	61.66	5
DCB	56.38	57.94	60.90	58.39	62.99	64.87	67.59	65.78	67.29	65.85	65.82	65.55	4

TABLE: 5 (Overall Capital Adequacy Rank)

BANK	CAR RANK	DER RANK	GSTI RANK	TADVTA	AVG RANK	FINAL RANK
CSB	3	3	7	3	4	4
CUB	7	1	1	1	2.5	1
DB	1	7	5	8	5.25	6.5
JKB	4	2	8	7	5.25	6.5
KB	2	4	4	6	4	3
KVB	5	5	3	2	3.75	2
SIB	6	6	2	5	4.75	5
DCB	8	8	6	4	6.5	8

Interpretation: from the above table, it is clear that city union bank is top most priority bank among the selected small cap private sector bank while Dhanlakmi and Jammu Kashmir bank both are in trouble zone from overall capital adequacy angle.

Asset quality ratios: To regard for the extent of Non-Performing Asset in the portfolios of the banks and the extent of damage this particular asset class can have on the fiscal performance the following rates like net NPA to net advance ratio, total investment to total asset ratio, gross NPA to total Advances ratio etc. are being considered and calculated for the purpose. The banks are being ranked accordingly and shown in the respective tables given below.

Table:6 (Net NPA to Net Advance Ratio = $\frac{\text{Gross NPA-Provisions}}{\text{Net Advance}}$)

BANK	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	AVG	RANK
------	------	------	------	------	------	------	------	------	------	------	------	-----	------

CSB	1.74	1.1	1.12	2.22	3.85	4.40	5.51	4.46	2.27	1.91	1.17	2.20	5
CUB	0.52	0.44	0.63	1.23	1.3	1.53	1.71	1.7	1.81	2.29	2.97	1.43	2
DB	0.3	0.66	3.36	3.8	3.29	2.78	2.58	3.19	2.41	1.55	4.76	2.59	8
JKB	0.2	0.15	0.14	0.91	2.77	4.31	4.87	4.89	4.89	3.48	2.95	2.26	7
KB	1.62	2.11	1.51	0.22	1.98	2.35	2.64	2.96	2.95	3.08	3.18	2.18	4
KVB	0.07	0.33	0.37	1.91	0.78	0.55	2.53	4.16	4.98	3.92	3.41	2.21	6
SIB	0.29	0.28	0.78	0.41	0.96	2.89	1.45	2.6	3.45	3.34	4.71	1.87	3
DCB	0.97	0.57	0.75	0.78	1.01	0.75	0.79	0.72	0.65	1.16	2.29	0.99	1

Interpretation: DCB bank having rank 1 is the best bank to handle NPA followed by city union bank on the other hand Dhanlaxmi bank & Jammu Kashmir banks are worst performer.

Table:7 (Total investment to total asset ratio= $\frac{\text{Total Investment}}{\text{Total Asset}} \times 100$)

BAN K	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	AVG	RAN K
CSB	29.77	27.37	26.11	24.24	38.54	32.06	38.25	35.51	25.92	25.25	28.41	26.25	3
CUB	27.77	24.78	24.99	22.92	23.82	22.84	20.24	19.94	19.73	17.04	18.57	17.70	8
DB	25.07	25.51	29.71	33.90	30.52	33.80	30.43	34.01	35.52	34.21	30.02	33.89	2
JKB	32.80	39.00	35.87	35.87	33.31	33.02	25.36	25.96	21.05	22.84	21.17	256.47	1
KB	36.98	36.31	35.35	32.35	32.38	30.84	28.77	31.53	21.95	20.48	21.06	25.28	4
KVB	30.10	27.39	27.92	29.61	25.70	24.03	22.93	24.04	23.61	21.46	23.09	21.47	6
SIB	28.02	27.19	23.28	25.15	26.10	28.28	23.14	26.15	22.21	20.68	21.26	21.58	5
DCB	32.88	31.13	29.02	29.78	28.12	27.71	22.67	24.19	20.58	21.92	20.11	21.25	7

Interpretation: From table 7 it is clear that Jammu Kasmir bank having rank 1 followed by Dhanlaxmi bank rank 2 on the other hand city union bank needs to focus how effectively bank manage its investments.

Table: 8 (gross NPA to Total Advances= $\frac{\text{Gross NPA}}{\text{Total Advances}}$)

BAN K	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	AVG	RAN K
CSB	3.09	2.39	2.38	3.83	5.01	5.69	7.39	0.82	5.00	3.34	2.56	3.77	4
CUB	1.22	1.02	1.41	1.82	1.86	2.41	2.83	3.03	2.95	4.09	5.11	2.52	1
DB	0.74	1.19	4.89	6.12	7.28	6.60	4.90	7.68	7.88	6.18	9.68	5.74	7
JKB	1.98	1.56	1.64	1.69	6.20	8.70	12.04	105.54	9.39	11.91	10.40	15.55	8
KB	4.05	3.30	2.53	2.95	2.98	3.48	4.27	5.03	4.48	4.92	5.01	3.91	5
KVB	1.28	1.34	0.97	0.82	1.88	1.31	3.63	6.73	9.16	9.14	8.23	4.04	6
SIB	1.12	0.98	1.36	1.19	1.72	3.80	2.48	3.63	5.00	5.06	7.14	3.04	3
DCB	6.16	4.58	3.26	1.70	1.78	1.53	1.61	1.81	1.86	2.49	4.17	2.81	2

Table: 9 (Overall Asset Quality Rank)

BANK	Net NPA to net adv rank	Total invest to total asset rank	Gross NPA to total advance rank	Average rank	Final rank
CSB	5	3	4	4	4
CUB	2	8	1	1	1
DB	6	2	7	7	7
JKB	5	1	8	8	8
KB	3	4	5	5	5
KVB	3	6	6	6	6
SIB	2	5	3	3	3
DCB	1	7	2	2	2

Interpretation: city union bank is best bank from the asset quality point of view followed by DCB on the other side J&K and Dhanlaxmi banks needs to give more attention on their asset quality.

Management Efficiency: The operation dimension in CAMEL analysis has assumed much important position like no way ahead. To capture the possible dynamics of operation effectiveness affecting the fiscal performance of the banks the following ratios Like, Profit per employee rate, business per employee rate, operating profit to total assets ratio, CASA rate, total expenditure to total assets, total income to total assets and total advances to total deposit ratio are considered and calculated in the respective tables drawn below.

Table: 10 (Profit per employee = $\frac{\text{Total Profit}}{\text{Total Number of employees}}$)

BA NK	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	AV G	R A N K
CSB	0.045	0.1	0.12	0.09	-0.18	-0.52	0.01	-0.35	-0.66	0.04	0.52	-0.03	7
CU B	0.8	0.8	0.9	0.8	0.9	1.00	1.10	1.1	0.12	8.3	0.1	1.54	1
DB	0.071	-0.33	0.01	-1.04	-1.06	-1.00	0.10	-13.2	0.1	0.4	0.2	-1.65	8
JKB	0.8	0.9	1.1	0.6	0.5	0.40	-1.60	0.2	0.4	-0.9	0.4	0.44	5
KB	0.4	0.4	0.5	1.3	0.6	0.50	0.60	0.4	0.6	0.5	0.57	0.59	2
KV B	0.91	0.88	0.82	0.4	0.65	0.79	0.82	0.44	0.27	0.29	0.46	0.57	3
SIB	0.5	0.7	0.8	0.59	0.4	0.40	0.50	0.4	0.3	0.1	0.08	0.43	6
DC B	0.1	0.2	0.5	0.7	0.6	0.50	0.40	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.53	0.46	4

Interpretation: From table 10 city union bank has efficient employees whereas the Dhanlaxmi and CSB has serious issues among the employees of the bank.

Table:11 (Business per employee = $\frac{\text{Total Income}}{\text{Total number of employees}} \times 100$)

BAN K	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	AVG	RAN K
CSB	53.7	67.5	73.6	77.1	78.95	77.54	85.93	85.12	85.87	85.2	80	76.34	7
CUB	78.1	84.7	93.8	90.6	96.5	106.9	115.3	114.	129.	131.	139.	106.5	5

						0	0	8	6	3	4	3	
DB	58.92 2	59.2 9	72.9 7	77.4 3	89.9 7	83.60	88.50	91.9	97.2	103. 3	113. 7	84.96	6
JKB	85.6	88.6	104. 9	68.9	114. 3	113.7 0	122.0 0	119. 9	123. 7	128. 5	144. 8	108.8 0	4
KB	77.1	85.9	96.6	117. 4	105. 2	108.3 0	113.7 0	134. 5	148. 9	151. 2	151. 2	118.6 7	2
KVB	93.5	98.4	101. 4	95.9	113	124.1 0	128.5 0	129. 2	144. 2	135. 4	149. 9	117.8 8	3
SIB	91.8	107. 9	120. 1	105. 5	115. 4	125.5 0	148.4 0	163. 2	172. 5	173. 8	173. 6	135.9 8	1
DCB	50.6	51.4	67.4	119. 9	69.6	67.80	68.50	72.3	79.2	80.4	83.2 1	74.89	8

Interpretation: south Indian bank's employees are generating more income for the banks on the other hand CSB and DCB employees are not effective for generating business income so management needs to focus on this.

Table:12 (Operating profit to total asset= $\frac{\text{operating income}}{\text{total asset}}$)

BA NK	201 0	201 1	201 2	201 3	201 4	201 5	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	AV G	RAN K
CS B	0.3 8	0.8 5	0.7 9	0.6 6	0.3 2	- 0.02	0.95	0.46	0.08	1.57	2.91	0.89	7
CU B	2.7 6	2.5 9	2.5 3	2.4 2	2.6 6	2.79	2.96	3.21	2.91	2.82	2.88	2.75	1
DB	0.6	- .68	0.3 6	0.0 4	0.1 8	0.00	0.76	1.19	0.79	1.35	0.83	0.52	8
JK B	2.4 7	2.4 7	2.7 4	1.5 5	2.3 7	2.14	1.60	1.61	1.8	1.45	1.41	1.99	3
KB	1.2 1	1.5	1.6 3	2.5 3	1.5 6	1.58	1.65	2.19	1.94	2.04	2.37	1.89	4
KV B	2.3 9	2.2	2.0 1	1.5 5	1.8 2	2.32	2.60	2.76	2.51	2.56	2	2.20	2
SIB	1.8	1.7 8	1.8 8	1.7	1.5 5	1.43	1.76	1.89	1.42	1.74	1.69	1.72	5
DC B	1.2 7	1.0 4	1.2 6	1.6 9	1.9 1	1.98	1.94	1.93	1.96	2.03	2.3	1.71	6

Interpretation: city union bank rank is 1 followed by karur vysya bank rank is 2 signifies that these two banks are utilizing effectively its asset to create income.

Table: 13 (CASA Rate = $\frac{\text{CASA Deposits}}{\text{Total Deposits}}$)

BAN K	201 0	201 1	201 2	201 3	201 4	201 5	201 6	201 7	201 8	201 9	202 0	AVEAR GE	RAN K
CSB	22.3 6	19.3 2	17.5 3	17.2 7	18	20.0 3	24.7 8	27.0 3	27.8 4	29.1 7	32.1 9	23.41	6
CUB	19.5 8	18.1 9	16.7 7	17.7 9	19.2 3	20.3 7	23.3 7	24.2 2	25.2 2	24.9 7	29.1 5	21.68	8
DB	22.9	19.3 5	22.4 6	21.9 9	24.3 4	25.0 3	29.4 4	30.8	32.0 1	29.8	33.3 7	26.34	3
JKB	40.4 8	40.7 1	39.2 3	25	41.7 9	44.1 3	51.7 0	50.8 9	50.7	53.6 6	56.8 4	44.37	1
KB	24.8 8	24.5 6	24.9 1	39.0 6	24.9 4	26.2 6	29.0 4	27.9 8	28.0 6	28.9 1	31.4 9	28.31	2

KVB	23.2 8	19.1 6	19.2 5	25.4	22.0 2	23.3 1	27.7 3	29.1 4	29.9 2	31.3 3	34.2 2	25.97	4
SIB	21.5 5	19.6 7	18.6	20.5 4	20.5 9	22.3 6	23.8 2	23.8	24.2 1	25	29.7 3	22.63	7
DCB	35.2 1	32.1 2	27.1 6	20.6 9	23.4	23.3 8	24.3 1	24.3 3	23.9 5	21.4 7	22.8 5	25.69	5

Interpretation: table 13 shows that, J&K bank and Karnataka banks are able to maintain good number of current account in their banks while city union bank and south Indian banks are worst performer.

Table:14 (Total expenditure to total income = $\frac{\text{Total expenditure}}{\text{Total Income}} \times 100$)

BAN K	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	AV G	RAN K
CSB	98.8 2	95.9 8	91.9 4	92.8 0	94.1 2	103. 18	100. 24	99.9 0	106. 85	99.1 0	83.8 0	73.0 2	1
CUB	76.7 5	73.7 6	77.5 7	78.7 4	79.5 9	87.2 4	75.1 6	86.2 5	84.9 5	84.0 5	72.3 4	87.7 5	3
DB	96.2 7	97.5 1	107. 52	99.8 2	118. 45	117. 64	116. 34	98.9 7	102. 23	98.8 6	94.0 2	96.5 3	7
JKB	84.3 2	84.9 1	84.4 7	72.6 7	83.5 0	93.3 6	94.3 4	122. 74	97.1 5	94.5 2	112. 67	81.7 5	2
KB	92.9 0	92.3 2	92.8 6	91.6 4	85.3 6	91.3 3	92.5 0	92.4 6	94.8 9	93.0 9	94.5 1	93.7 6	5
KVB	83.2 3	83.2 4	86.1 4	88.2 8	92.4 4	92.3 8	90.7 7	90.5 4	94.7 3	96.8 9	75.3 6	94.4 8	6
SIB	89.1 0	88.9 3	89.5 1	89.4 7	90.5 7	94.6 9	94.5 1	94.0 2	95.2 4	96.7 4	98.8 1	99.2 7	8
DCB	113. 85	96.7 0	93.2 8	90.1 2	88.0 5	87.9 6	89.8 6	91.4 1	90.9 9	90.4 1	91.4 0	91.4 3	4

Interpretation: CSB and J&K banks are most cost effective while south Indian bank and Dhanlaxmi banks are less cost effective.

Table: 15 (Total income to total asset ratio = $\frac{\text{Total Income}}{\text{Total Asset}}$)

BAN K	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	AV G	RAN K
CSB	8.48	8.51	9.64	10.3 9	12.1 8	10.6 1	10.1 4	9.97	8.96	8.77	9.18	9.74	2
CUB	9.52	9.43	10.3 7	10.7 2	11.3 9	11.1 3	10.7 3	10.3 7	9.85	9.46	9.75	9.08	3
DB	7.74	7.38	10.4 7	10.2 9	9.30	9.54	10.2 8	9.73	9.08	8.68	8.97	8.19	7
JKB	8.16	8.07	8.58	9.23	9.11	10.0 6	9.16	8.75	7.93	8.37	8.26	7.34	8
KB	8.71	8.40	9.49	10.0 2	9.98	10.0 4	9.80	9.35	9.06	8.74	9.45	9.03	4
KVB	9.14	8.79	9.62	10.0 5	11.0 2	11.2 4	10.6 7	10.3 6	9.86	9.78	10.4 6	8.75	6
SIB	8.40	8.05	9.49	9.58	9.79	9.78	9.62	8.83	8.50	8.24	9.08	9.02	5
DCB	9.23	8.79	9.45	9.16	9.80	9.84	10.0 4	9.67	9.01	9.48	10.2 0	9.89	1

Interpretation: the above table shows that DCB & CSB are effectively utilize their asset for generating income whereas J&K bank and Dhanlaxmi bank are fails to do so.

Table:16 (Total advances to total deposit ratio = $\frac{\text{Total Advances}}{\text{Total Deposit}} \times 100$)

BANK	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	AVG	RANK
CSB	64.01	71.28	72.26	71.72	70.55	65.44	54.39	54.45	635.33	70.19	77.51	80.40	3
CUB	66.44	71.67	74.28	60.31	73.11	75.14	78.26	80.06	85.96	86.00	84.68	83.12	2
DB	70.53	72.35	74.20	69.42	65.41	61.94	61.24	57.08	55.96	59.31	59.57	57.95	8
JKB	61.92	58.63	62.00	61.04	66.90	67.80	72.33	68.75	71.09	73.93	65.86	61.86	7
KB	60.83	63.46	65.55	69.91	69.85	68.86	67.15	65.22	75.16	80.10	79.35	68.33	6
KVB	69.77	72.06	74.58	76.27	77.68	80.80	78.05	76.18	78.75	81.15	78.03	79.59	4
SIB	68.76	68.94	74.74	71.88	76.29	72.03	73.74	70.16	75.75	77.96	77.61	70.19	5
DCB	72.27	76.14	83.41	78.74	78.84	83.00	86.57	82.00	84.71	82.88	83.46	87.39	1

Interpretation: From table 16 it is confirm that DCB bank & city union bank are effectively handle their deposits for earning interest in the form of providing advances. J&K bank and Dhanlaxmi bank needs to focus on this aspect as their rank is 8 and 7 respectively.

Table: 17 (Overall Management Quality)

Bank	Profit per employee rank	Business per employee	Operating profit to total asset	Cas a ratio	Total advances to total deposit	Total income to total asset	Total expenditure to total income	Average rank	Final rank
CSB	7	7	7	6	3	2	1	4.714286	6
CUB	1	5	1	8	2	3	3	3.285714	1
DB	8	6	8	3	8	7	7	6.714286	8
JKB	5	4	3	1	7	8	2	4.285714	5
KB	2	2	4	2	6	4	5	3.571429	2
KVB	3	3	2	4	4	6	6	4	3
SIB	6	1	5	7	5	5	8	5.285714	7
DCB	4	8	6	5	1	1	4	4.142857	4

Interpretation: city union bank and Karnataka banks are effectively managed whereas, Dhanlaxmi bank & south Indian banks management needs to cautious as their rank is 8 and 7.

Earning Quality: Banks depend on their strong capability of earnings for performing the conditioning like funding tips, maintaining acceptable capital situations, furnishing for openings of investment for bank to grow, strategies for engaging in new conditioning and maintaining the competitive outlook. However apart from the sources of earning, the following dimensions also decide significantly the fiscal performance of the banks. Position, trend, and stability of earnings ,

Quality and sources of earnings , Capability to compound capital through retained earnings, Exposure to market risks ,Provisions for loan losses. Keeping in horizon the above mentioned dynamics the following rates like, net profit to asset ratio, return on equity ratio, interest income to total income ratio, non-interest income to total income ratio in the dimension of earning capability of the banks to measure fiscal performance are considered and the ratios, ranks as per the ratios are given in the following tables.

Table:18 (Net profit to Asset ratio: **Net profit/ total asset**)

BAN K	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	AV G	RAN K
CSB	0.02	0.12	0.21	0.24	0.20	-	-	0.01	-	-1.17	0.07	0.93	3
CUB	1.32	1.47	1.53	1.40	1.39	1.42	1.42	1.43	1.48	1.51	0.96	1.11	2
DB	0.29	0.18	-	0.02	-	-	-	0.10	-	0.10	0.54	0.28	7
JKB	1.28	1.22	1.33	2.52	1.50	0.67	0.52	-	0.23	0.46	-1.05	1.34	1
KB	0.62	0.65	0.68	0.84	1.46	0.87	0.74	0.71	0.46	0.60	0.52	0.56	5
KVB	1.53	1.47	1.33	1.18	0.83	0.86	0.98	0.98	0.52	0.30	2.58	0.48	6
SIB	0.92	0.89	0.99	1.01	0.92	0.52	0.53	0.53	0.41	0.27	0.11	0.07	8
DCB	-	0.29	0.63	0.90	1.17	1.19	1.02	0.83	0.81	0.91	0.88	0.85	4
	1.28												

Interpretation: From table 18 it shows that Jammu Kashmir bank followed by city union bank are effectively utilize asset to get more return on contrary the south India and Dhanlaxmi banks need to focus on the utilization of asset effectively.

Table: 19 (Return on Equity= $\frac{\text{Net Income}}{\text{Share holder Equity}}$)

BAN K	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	AV G	RAN K
CSB	2.6	4.66	4.94	3.52	-	-	0.16	-	-	0.75	10.5	-	7
					6.41	16.8		10.3	17.0		5	0.75	
CUB	23.4	24.9	22.3	18.9	16.7	15.4	15.1	15.3	15.1	9.4	10.6	17.4	1
	7	1	3	4	4	7	8	1	7		4	3	
DB	4.06	-	0.35	-	-	-	2.13	-	1.54	8.28	4.4	-	8
		14.7		33.5	33.0	34.0		3.54				7.36	
JKB	18.9	21.2	23.5	14.0	8.6	6.64	-	3.42	7.27	-	6.54	9.57	6
	6	2	6	3			26.9			17.5			
KB	9.6	9.79	12.7	22.3	14.0	11.7	10.2	6.17	8.53	7.35	7.65	10.9	3
			6	4	2	3	4					1	
KVB	22.1	20.8	19	10.5	12.2	12.8	12.6	6.12	3.32	3.61	5.3	11.4	2
	2	1		3	6	7	1					5	
SIB	17.5	19.9	19.4	13.4	8.82	8.96	9.03	6.64	4.68	1.93	1.1	10.3	4
	6	9	1									9	
DCB	3.51	7.43	10.9	15.9	13.9	11.5	9.99	9.79	10.9	10.3	9.35	10.2	5
			5	2	4	1			9	4		5	

Interpretation: Table 19 shows that the investor may prefer to invest in city union bank, Karur Vyasya bank than the others but they may hesitate to invest in CSB or Dhanlaxmi bank.

Table:20 (Interest Income to total income ration = $\frac{\text{Interest income}}{\text{Total income}} \times 100$)

BAN	201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201	201	202	AVEAR	RAN
-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-------	-----

K	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	GE	K
CSB	88.6 5	91.1 0	92.6 6	93.3 2	92.7 6	92.3 8	93.4 1	82.6 2	91.1 8	90.8 4	87.2 0	82.37	7
CUB	86.9 5	88.5 6	89.1 2	88.8 9	89.3 9	86.9 8	87.7 8	86.7 9	86.4 8	87.9 9	85.9 7	85.45	5
DB	85.4 6	86.0 7	90.6 6	91.9 6	94.6 2	93.7 9	94.0 1	90.7 5	90.8 2	94.8 5	89.7 5	86.81	3
JKB	88.0 2	91.0 6	93.5 2	92.6 7	94.5 1	92.2 4	93.1 4	93.1 3	93.0 4	90.4 3	93.9 3	91.86	1
KB	83.9 2	89.0 4	90.3 0	90.4 5	89.2 3	90.2 6	90.1 9	86.5 0	85.0 4	85.5 0	82.2 6	80.65	8
KVB	87.6 7	89.3 2	90.3 3	90.3 6	90.0 6	90.2 8	88.5 1	87.7 9	86.3 6	85.8 0	83.8 4	83.81	6
SIB	90.2 8	92.5 6	93.5 5	92.9 8	93.1 6	91.4 1	91.4 8	89.1 0	88.0 9	90.4 5	88.1 3	86.04	4
DCB	81.0 2	82.7 1	87.4 7	88.6 7	89.0 6	89.5 7	88.5 1	89.2 7	88.6 1	89.6 8	90.0 4	88.29	2

Interpretation: As table 20 shows J&K bank is rank 1 followed by DCB rank is 2 so these bank are focusing more on core area on the other side Karnataka bank and CSB are having rank 8 and 7 so these banks should bed focus on core area of bank.

Table: 21 (Non-interest income to total income ratio: $\frac{\text{non interest income}}{\text{total income}}$)

BAN K	2010	2011	2012	2013	201 4	201 5	201 6	201 7	201 8	201 9	2020	AV G	RAN K
CSB	11.3 5	8.90	7.34	6.68	7.2 4	7.62	6.5 9	17.3 8	8.8 2	9.16	12.8 0	17.6 3	2
CUB	13.0 4	11.4 4	10.8 8	11.1 1	10. 61	13.0 2	12. 22	13.2 1	13. 52	12.0 1	14.0 3	14.5 5	4
DB	14.5 4	13.9 3	9.34	8.04	5.3 8	6.21	5.9 9	9.25	9.1 8	5.15	10.2 5	13.1 9	6
JKB	11.9 8	8.94	6.48	7.33	5.4 9	7.76	6.8 6	6.87	6.9 6	9.57	6.07	8.14	8
KB	16.0 8	10.9 6	9.70	9.55	10. 77	9.74	9.8 1	13.5 0	14. 96	14.5 0	17.7 4	19.3 5	1
KVB	12.3 3	10.6 8	9.67	9.64	9.9 4	9.72	11. 49	12.2 1	13. 64	14.2 0	16.1 6	16.1 9	3
SIB	9.72	7.44	6.45	7.02	6.8 4	8.59	8.5 2	10.9 0	11. 91	9.55	11.8 7	13.9 6	5
DCB	18.9 8	17.2 9	12.5 3	11.3 3	10. 94	10.4 3	11. 49	10.7 3	11. 39	10.3 2	9.96	11.7 1	7

Table: 22 (Overall Earning Perspective)

BANK	RETURN ON EQUITY RANK	NET PROFIT TO ASSET RANK	INTREST INCOME TO TOTAL INCOME	NON INTREST INCOME TO TOTAL INCOME	AVERAGE RANK	FINAL RANK
CSB	7	3	7	2	4.75	6
CUB	1	2	5	4	3	1
DB	8	7	3	6	6	8
JKB	6	1	1	8	4	2

KB	3	5	8	1	4.25	3.5
KVB	2	6	6	3	4.25	3.5
SIB	4	8	4	5	5.25	7
DCB	5	4	2	7	4.5	5

Interpretation: From table 22 it is clear that city union bank is best from earning perspective followed by J&K bank at the same time South Indian bank & Dhanlaxmi bank are the worst.

Liquidity: Liquidity operation in banks has assumed high significance due to competitive pressure and the easy inflow of foreign capital in the domestic markets. The impact of liquidity extremity in the banks can negatively impact the fiscal performance of the banks. To capture the impact of liquidity on the fiscal performance of the banks the ratios like: government securities to total asset ratio, total investments to total deposit rate and liquid asset to total asset ratio are being calculated and ranked the banks accordingly in the respective tables below.

Table: 23 (Government securities to total asset = $\frac{\text{Govt.securities}}{\text{Total asset}} \times 100$)

BAN K	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	AV G	RAN K
CSB	23.42	22.12	23.16	21.69	26.47	25.65	31.22	31.17	21.36	19.89	24.62	19.45	6
CUB	22.23	19.77	20.96	19.86	21.28	19.69	18.89	18.97	19.12	16.52	17.97	17.50	7
DB	20.77	23.19	28.37	31.52	25.74	25.69	24.65	25.36	24.72	24.18	19.90	30.12	1
JKB	19.84	20.44	19.16	19.60	19.01	17.68	17.38	19.90	19.17	18.25	19.03	25.17	2
KB	23.69	21.13	22.39	21.35	22.19	22.09	20.47	21.65	18.61	17.26	18.37	22.49	3
KVB	25.91	23.96	24.59	27.02	23.66	21.66	21.09	20.86	20.94	18.27	19.35	20.02	5
SIB	22.03	20.69	20.34	20.05	20.92	20.89	21.90	22.94	19.49	18.16	19.77	20.34	4
DCB	25.52	23.69	23.30	21.57	21.72	21.54	20.85	19.84	16.24	16.77	15.94	17.01	8

Interpretation: above table shows that DCB and City union bank are more prone to risk as these two banks are less expose toward government securities.

Table:24 (Total investment to total deposit ratio = $\frac{\text{Total investment}}{\text{Total deposit}} \times 100$)

BAN K	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	AVE	RAN K
CSB	32.81	30.83	29.66	26.75	41.58	34.91	41.46	38.64	28.00	28.24	33.94	32.01	3
CUB	31.21	28.00	28.07	25.94	27.04	26.45	23.29	23.35	23.98	20.06	22.62	21.19	8
DB	25.07	25.51	29.71	33.90	30.52	33.80	30.43	34.01	35.52	34.21	30.02	33.89	2
JKB	37.48	44.09	40.53	40.07	37.77	38.21	29.33	29.38	235.82	25.84	23.57	285.50	1
KB	36.98	36.31	35.35	32.35	32.38	30.84	28.77	31.53	21.95	20.48	21.06	25.28	6
KVB	34.26	31.27	32.72	35.80	30.27	28.58	26.40	27.67	27.78	24.86	26.68	25.31	5
SIB	31.10	30.03	25.75	28.29	30.22	32.20	26.24	29.39	25.49	23.73	24.84	24.57	7

DCB	42.1 5	40.9 1	39.7 4	40.1 6	35.2 0	35.4 5	29.0 3	30.1 6	25.90	27.5 9	25.4 9	28.33	4
-----	-----------	-----------	-----------	-----------	-----------	-----------	-----------	-----------	-------	-----------	-----------	-------	---

Interpretation: Both J&k bank and Dhanlaxmi bank’s rankings indicates that they are maintaining better liquidity position but City union bank and south Indian banks are prone to liquidity risk.

Table:25 (Liquid asset to total asset ratio= $\frac{\text{Liquid Asset}}{\text{Total Asset}}$)

BANK	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	AVG	RANK
CSB	6.16	6.13	5.01	8.07	7.38	18.0 5	20.2 9	17.0 5	15.9 8	17.6 3	17.2 9	12.6 4	1
CUB	8.81	6.18	7.70	11.3 8	10.9 5	10.9 0	13.2 0	11.6 8	13.9 3	15.8 6	17.8 4	11.6 8	2
DB	0.93	6.31	5.51	11.2 2	8.99	6.68	6.55	7.09	5.28	9.21	7.52	6.84	3
JKB	7.03	7.39	7.53	5.36	4.91	3.99	6.57	9.21	5.78	8.99	7.9	6.79	4
KB	6.27	5.14	4.7	4.97	5.04	5.39	5.11	5.12	4.57	3.5	6.21	5.09	8
KVB	4.38	5.41	3.84	5.2	5.17	4.84	7.03	6.42	5.33	6.43	8.47	5.68	7
SIB	7.51	6.54	8.71	5.85	6.08	4.91	5.23	5.1	5.23	4.32	9.31	6.25	6
DCB	6.61	5.26	7.83	5.34	4.46	4.66	4.96	7.85	7.8	9.21	7.67	6.51	5

Interpretation: In table 25 CSB having rank 1 followed by CUB rank 2 signifies that these banks are more liquid asset in their total asset but J&K bank and Karur vysya bank are assigned rank 8 and 7 needs to maintain liquidity in their total assets.

Table: 26 (Overall Liquidity Rank)

Bank	Liquid asset to total asset rank	Gov. securities to total asset	Total investment to total deposit	Average rank	Final rank
CSB	1	3	3	2.333333333	1.5
CUB	2	8	8	6	7
DB	3	2	2	2.333333333	1.5
JKB	4	7	1	4	3
KB	8	4	6	6	7
KVB	7	1	5	4.333333333	4
SIB	6	5	7	6	7
DCB	5	6	4	5	5

Interpretation: Table 26 shows that CSB and Dhanlaxmi bank are maintaining high liquidity on the other hand city union bank and south Indian bank are in a difficult position to maintain liquidity.

Table: 27 (CAMEL Rank)

BANK	C	A	M	E	L	AVERAGE	OVER ALL RANK
CSB	4	4	6	6	1.5	4.3	4
CUB	1	1	1	1	7	2.2	1
DB	6.5	7	8	8	1.5	6.2	8
JKB	6.5	8	5	2	3	4.9	6
KB	3	5	2	3.5	7	4.1	3
KVB	2	6	3	3.5	4	3.7	2
SIB	5	3	7	7	7	5.8	7
DCB	8	2	4	5	5	4.8	5

Conclusion:

From table 27 the camel score reflecting that City union bank is the no1 bank in overall ranking and best among the small cap private sector bank on the other hand Dhanlaxmi bank is the worst performer on the basis of camel score. So investor must be cautious while investing their money in the particular bank. City union bank have potential to become mid cap or large cap bank in near future. The limitation of this study is that it covers only selected private sector small cap bank due to non-availability of data further the researcher conclude that not only CAMEL approach but also there are other econometric model which shall be used in future in order to derive correct conclusion about the financial health of these banks.

BIBLIOGRAPHY:

- 1.Bansal, S., & Khosla, D. (2015). *Multivariate analysis of Indian banking sector performance : A camel framework approach*. 2(1), 362–366.
- 2.Das, A., & Ghosh, S. (2006). *Financial deregulation and efficiency : An empirical analysis of Indian banks during the post reform period* B. 15, 193–221. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rfe.2005.06.002>
- 3.Dr. R. Thamil selvan1, d. J. K. (2011). *Performance evaluation of selected indian commercial*. 32(2), 1929–1936.
- 4.Gandhi, V., Chhajaj, P., & Mehta, V. (2020). *Post-Merger Financial Performance of Indian Banks : Camel Approach*. 8(2), 2020.
- 5.Mishra, M. K. (2017). *Analysing Soundness and Efficiency of Banking in India*. 07(02), 24–31.
- 6.Mohammed, S., Sha, N., Said, J., & Al, M. (2019). *Analyzing the Financial Soundness of Bank Dhofar : A CAMEL Approach*. XVIII(4), 2019.
- 7.Nguyen, T. T. C., Nguyen, T. H. P., Nguyen, T. B. T., Selvarajan, S. K., & Baskaran, A. (2022). The impact of opportunity factors on fraudulent behavior in the Vietnamese stock market. *Journal of Asian Economics*, 79, 101451.
- 8.Ray, M. (2021). *Financial Analysis of Small Finance Banks in India through CAMEL Rating*. December.

Websites:

- <https://www.csb.co.in/investor-relations> retrieved on 12/03/2022
- <https://www.cityunionbank.com/investor/about-cub/annual-results> retrieved on 12/03/2022
- https://www.dhanbank.com/investor_relations/inv_financials.aspx retrieved on 12/03/2022
- <https://www.jkbank.com/investor/financials/annualReports.php> retrieved on 12/03/2022
- <https://karnatakabank.com/investor-portal/annual-report> retrieved on 12/03/2022
- <https://www.kvb.co.in/investor-corner/annual-general-meeting/agm-annual-reports/> retrieved on 12/03/2022
- <https://www.southindianbank.com/content/investor-desk-annual-reports/911> retrieved on 12/03/2022
- <https://www.dccb.com/about-us-key-financials> retrieved on 12/03/2022
- <https://www.indiastat.com/data/banks-and-financial-institutions/financial-ratios-of-private-sector-banks> retrieved on 16/03/2022
- <https://rbi.org.in/Scripts/Statistics.aspx> retrieved on 16/03/2022